

ANTIBIOGRAM AND BIOFILM FORMATION POTENTIALS OF *Klebsiella* species ISOLATED FROM READY TO EAT *Rhynchophorus phoenicis* (Edible worm) AND *Archachatina marginata* (African Land Snail)

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ABSTRACT

Drug resistance and biofilm formation among foodborne pathogens has become a serious cause for concern and ready to eat foods have been identified as a source of such foodborne pathogens. *Klebsiella* spp., a recognized food borne pathogen is emerging as a pathogen that has the capacity to develop multi-drug antibiotic resistance and produce biofilms. Ready to eat *Rhynchophorus phoenicis* (edible worm) and *Archachatina marginata* (snail) sold along the Benin/Warri road in southern Nigeria were investigated for the presence of *Klebsiella* spp., antibiotic resistance pattern of the isolates and the ability of the isolates to produce biofilms. The result of the investigation shows that over 95% of the samples had *Klebsiella* spp. isolated from them with edible worm samples recording 100% prevalence rate. Result of the antibiotic resistance pattern of the *Klebsiella* spp. isolates from the various sources shows that over 75% of the isolates were resistant to cefuroxime, amoxicillin, ampicillin, doxycycline and cloxacillin, with all the isolates from edible worm recording 100% resistance to ampicillin. All the isolates irrespective of the source were however susceptible to gentamycin, ofloxacin and ciprofloxacin. Biofilm formation capability result indicate that almost all the isolates were strong biofilm producers irrespective of the surface. The investigation reveal that surfaces differ in their affinity for biofilm formation by microorganisms as the result shows that plastic are better surfaces for biofilm production by the isolates than aluminum surfaces. The findings from this study gives an indication that indiscriminate eating of road side hawked foods could pose serious health challenge as it clearly confirm not only the presence of proven pathogenic foodborne organisms but also the potentials for spreading antibiotic resistance among humans.

Key words: *Rhynchophorus phoenicis*, Snail, *Klebsiella* spp, Antibiotic Resistance, Biofilm

INTRODUCTION

Resistance can be referred to as the ability of a microorganism to grow in the presence of an elevated level of an antimicrobial agent, and the emergence of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a rapidly increasing challenge in today's healthcare delivery system worldwide. Most Pathogenic bacterial species are developing multidrug resistant (MDR) strains and this is a major challenge as they could pose a serious threat to efforts to treat patients that come up with infectious agents such as *Klebsiella* spp. that has the ability to easily develop resistance to commonly used antibiotics and produce biofilms.

A biofilm is a population of cells growing on a surface and enclosed in an exopolysaccharide matrix. Lopez *et al.* (2010), refer to biofilm as an association of micro-organisms in which microbial cells adhere to each other on living or non-living surfaces within a self-produced matrix of extracellular polymeric substance. They noted that formation of biofilm begins when free-floating microorganisms such as bacteria come in contact with a suitable surface and attach themselves after producing what they refer to as an extracellular polymeric substance. Lewis, (2001) indicated in his work that biofilms are notoriously difficult to eradicate and can be a source of many recalcitrant infections. This assertion was confirmed by Donlan, (2002) who posited that bacterial species possessing biofilms have the ability to share nutrients, and also poses shelter from harmful environmental factors, which might include desiccation, antibiotics, and the immune system of the host. He also noted that bacterial biofilm is infectious in nature, and could result in nosocomial infections.

Klebsiella is a genus of non-motile, gram negative, oxidase negative rod shape bacteria with a prominent polysaccharide capsule. The polysaccharide capsule encases the entire cell surface, and accounts for the large appearance of the organism on gram stain, and provides resistance against many host defense mechanisms. The genus typically express 2 types of antigens on their cell surface. The first is a lipopolysaccharide (O antigen) and the other is a capsular polysaccharide (K antigen). Both of these antigens are known to contribute to pathogenicity. The structural variability of these antigens forms the basis for classification into various serotypes. However the virulence of all serotypes reported appears to be similar (Bagley, 1985). Three species in the genus *Klebsiella* are majorly reported to be associated with illness in humans: *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Klebsiella oxytoca*, and *Klebsiella granulomatis*. They are recognized as a common cause of health-care associated infections and are also now known to be foodborne (Hatheway and Farmer, 1991; Sabota *et al.*, 1998; Hartantyo *et al.*, 2020). Most pathogenic members have been reputed to have high levels of antibiotic resistance and are also now known for their ability to produce biofilm (Nirwati *et al.* 2019)

Rhynochophorus phoenicis larva, popularly known as edible worm in Nigeria, is a large insect larva obtained from palm trees. Fazoranti, (1998), reported that most of them have length of about 3.5cm, a width of about 2.0cm and that they are found in a wide geographical location spanning many different

climatic regions such as Africa, Southern Asia and South America. Edible worms are cherished as food and it is a recognized delicacy by rural and urban dwellers among the Niger delta people of Nigeria where it is consumed mostly as ready to eat protein food.

Snail meat is a popular delicacy in several parts of Africa, and a common ready to eat food in most parts of Nigeria. Its high protein, low fat and cholesterol content make snails a nutritional favorite for health-conscious consumers as reported by Fasoranti, (1998). He stated further that snails are considered very nutritious because they contain the amino acids arginine and lysine at high levels, low fat, high protein content, magnesium, iron, and vitamins including linoleic acids. This makes them great alternative ready to eat foods especially as it can supply majority of the nutritional needs of the consumers.

Ready to eat foods are those produced for direct consumption without any need for further cooking or processing before they are consumed. It has been observed that most ready to eat foods such as edible worm and snails are hawked along the streets and major roads in Nigeria and poor handling of such foods makes them prone to microbial contamination with infectious agents, which has severally been proven to be responsible for major food borne infections with examples including organisms such as *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella* spp., *Klebsiella* spp. and a host of other pathogenic infectious agents. Foodborne diseases are an ever increasing problem involving a wide spectrum of illnesses as such adequate knowledge and an understanding of the major etiological agents responsible for food borne infections is required to enable informed decisions on how to control the problem. *Klebsiella* spp. though recognized for its pathogenic nature in clinical samples has not been adequately studied as a food borne pathogen. In view of the lack of adequate literature on its prevalence in food, especially in sub-Saharan Africa, this study is an attempt to add to the body of knowledge on the presence of the organism in food and also to sensitize consumers of ready to eat foods of the inherent danger of indiscriminate consumption of such food. The study is also aimed at investigating the antibiotic sensitivity pattern and the biofilm formation potential of *Klebsiella* spp. isolated from the ready to eat snail and edible worm sampled.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Samples

Ten (10) samples each of ready to eat edible worm (*Rhychosporous phoenicis*) and snail (*Archachatina marginata*) were purchased from hawkers along Sapele Road by Adesuwa junction, Benin City and Warri-Sapele Road, Amukpe Junction Sapele. The samples were collected in sterile foil paper and transported to the Benson Idahosa Microbiology Laboratory for immediate analysis

Isolation and Identification of *Klebsiella* spp.

Each sample was crushed with a sterile mortar, from which 5g was mixed with 45ml of buffered peptone water contained in a conical flask. This was properly homogenized using a vortex mixer, and labelled “stock “and thereafter left on the bench to incubate at room temperature of $26 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ for about 1 hour to resuscitate the organisms after which 1 g of the homogenate food sample was suspended in 9 ml buffered peptone water. Serial dilutions of up to 10^{-7} were then made and 1 ml of each dilution was plated on both Nutrient agar and MacConkey agar. They were then incubated at 37°C for 24h. Pure cultures of all organisms exhibiting thick mucoid pink colonies on the MacConkey agar plates which is characteristic of *Klebsiella* spp. on MacConkey agar were then made in readiness for biochemical tests. Counts of colonies growing on the nutrient agar were done and recorded for determination of the total heterotrophic count while counts on MacConkey agar were noted for calculation of the total *Klebsiella* count. Biochemical tests to confirm *Klebsiella* spp. was done in accordance with the method described by Holt *et al.* (1994).

Antibiotic Susceptibility Test

Antibiotics susceptibility test was performed using the disc diffusion method on Mueller Hinton agar. The isolates were inoculated into sterile nutrient broth in test tubes and incubated for 24h at 37°C . The cultures were adjusted to 0.5 McFarland standards after which 0.5 ml was spread evenly using a sterile glass rod on already solidified Mueller Hinton agar plates. Antibiotics disk were immediately placed on the agar plates with sterile forceps after which the plates were incubated for 24h at 37°C . The antibiotics multidisc (Abtek Biologicals Ltd) used contained Cloxacillin (OB, $5\mu\text{g}$), Cefuroxime

(CXM, 30µg), Gentamicin (CN, 30µg), Ofloxacin (OFX, 5µg), Ciprofloxacin (CIP, 5µg), Ampicillin (AMP, 10µg), Doxycycline (DO, 30µg) and Amoxycillin (AMC, 30µg). After incubation the diameter (in mm) of the zone around each disk was measured and interpreted in accordance with the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute Standards guidelines (CLSI). Interpretation of zones of inhibition are >18mm (sensitive), 13-17mm (intermediate) and < 13mm (resistant) (CLSI, 2015).

Test for Biofilm formation

The biofilm test was carried out using a slightly modified spectrophotometric assay method of Stepanović *et al.*, (2000). A colony of each isolate was cultured on nutrient agar slope, and then transferred into beakers containing 150ml of nutrient broth. The broth culture containing inoculum was incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Chips cut out from aluminum and PVC were washed using sterile distilled water and detergent, and autoclaved at 121°C for 15 min, after which the chips were aseptically placed in each of the beakers containing the broth cultures. This was closed tightly with a plug wrapped with aluminum foil and incubated at ambient temperature of $26 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24 hours. After incubation, the chips were aseptically removed from broth culture, washed 3 times with 5ml of sterile distilled water, after which the remaining adhered bacteria was fixed with 2.5ml of methanol per chip. Each chip was then stained with crystal violet for 15 minutes, and excess stain was washed off under running water and left to air dry. After air drying, the dye bound to the adherent cells was re-solubilized with 2.5ml of 33% glacial acetic acid for each chip. The re-solubilized liquid for each chip was then poured into a cuvette, after which the absorbance was measured against optical density (OD) at a wavelength of 620nm using a spectrophotometer.

RESULTS

The result of the total heterotrophic count on nutrient agar as shown in table 1 indicate that edible worm sampled from Benin had the highest average count of 1.46×10^6 cfu/g while snail also from Benin had the lowest average count of 1.03×10^6 cfu/g. Result of the total coliform count on MacConkey Agar as recorded in table 2, shows that edible worm also sampled from Benin had the

highest average count of 1.00×10^6 cfu/g while the lowest count of 0.73×10^6 cfu/g was recorded in snail sampled from Benin .

Analysis of the prevalence rate of *Klebsiella* spp. based on number of samples collected as shown in table 3, indicate that the organism was 100 percent present in all the samples collected except snail samples collected from Benin which had 90 percent prevalence rate.

Result of the antibiotic resistance pattern (table 4), shows that over 75% of the isolates were resistant to cefuroxime, amoxicillin, ampicillin doxycycline and cloxacillin, with isolates from edible worm recording 100% resistance to ampicillin. All the isolates were susceptible to gentamycin, ofloxacin and ciprofloxacin.

Biofilm formation capability results (tables 4 and 5) shows that almost all the isolates were capable of producing biofilm but at different degrees. Plastic surfaces had a higher affinity for biofilm formation by the isolates than Aluminum surfaces with average OD figures for aluminum ranging between 0.500 recorded from *Klebsiella* spp. isolates from edible worm in Benin and 0.934 recorded from isolates from snail also sampled from Benin. Average OD figures for Plastic surfaces ranged between 2.426 recorded for isolates from edible worm sampled from Benin and 3.173 recorded for isolates from snail sampled from Sapele. Statistically there was significant difference ($P < 0.05$, X^2) in biofilm formation capability between the Aluminum and the Plastic surfaces, however there was no significant difference ($P > 0.05$, X^2) between isolates from location and food type.

Table 1: Total Heterotrophic Count on Nutrient Agar

Sample	Benin ($\times 10^6$ cfu/g)		Sapele ($\times 10^6$ cfu/g)	
	Edible worm	Snail	Edible worm	Snail
H1	1.23	0.87	1.02	0.98
H2	1.15	1.11	1.15	0.94
H3	0.95	0.88	1.06	1.21
H4	1.07	0.77	1.21	1.10
H5	1.20	1.06	0.90	0.95
H6	1.84	0.94	1.06	1.92
H7	2.11	1.43	1.44	1.13
H8	0.99	0.96	2.25	0.88
H9	2.45	1.02	1.07	1.13
H10	1.64	1.22	1.98	0.65
Average count \pm SD	1.46 ± 0.52	1.03 ± 0.19	1.31 ± 0.45	1.09 ± 0.33

Table 2: Total Coliform Count on MacConkey Agar

Sample	Benin (x 10 ⁶ cfu/g)		Sapele (x 10 ⁶ cfu/g)	
	Edible worm	Snail	Edible worm	Snail
C1	1.16	0.72	0.99	0.81
C2	1.39	0.60	1.52	0.86
C3	1.19	0.62	0.89	0.88
C4	0.87	0.88	0.92	0.75
C5	0.75	0.63	0.80	0.82
C6	0.62	0.67	0.77	0.96
C7	0.97	1.14	0.45	0.74
C8	0.87	0.51	0.56	1.08
C9	1.02	1.17	0.68	0.58
C10	1.12	0.38	1.24	1.03
Average count ± SD	1.00 ± 0.23	0.73 ± 0.26	0.88 ± 0.32	0.85 ± 0.15

Table 3: Prevalence rate of *Klebsiella* spp. Isolated from edible worm and snail based on number of samples collected

Location	Prevalence rate (Number of sample n = 10)	
	Edible worm Number (%)	Snail Number (%)
Benin	10 (100)	9 (90)
Sapele	10(100)	10 (100)
Total	20 (100)	19 (95%)

Table 4: Antibiotic Resistance pattern of *Klebsiella* spp. Isolated from Edible worm and Snail

Antibiotics	Resistance pattern Number of isolate tested each n = 10				Mean resistance pattern Number (%)	
	Benin		Sapele		Edible worm	Snail
	Edible worm Number (%)	Snail Number (%)	Edible worm Number (%)	Snail Number (%)		
CXM (30µg)	8(80)	9(90)	9(90)	8(80)	8.5(85)	8.5(85)
AMC(30µg)	9(90)	8(80)	9(90)	7(70)	9(90)	7.5(75)
CN (30µg)	0(00)	0(00)	0(00)	0(00)	0(00)	0(00)
AMP(10µg)	10(100)	9(90)	10(100)	9(90)	10(100)	9(90)
DO(30µg)	8(80)	8(80)	10(100)	7(70)	9(90)	7.5(75)
OB(5µg)	8(80)	9(90)	7(70)	10(100)	7.5(75)	9.5(95)
OFX(5µg)	0(00)	0(00)	0(00)	0(00)	0(00)	0(00)
CIP(5µg)	0(00)	0(00)	0(00)	0(00)	0(00)	0(00)

Key: CXM: Cefuroxime, AMC: Amoxicillin, CN: Gentamycin, AMP: Ampicillin, DO: Doxycycline, OB: Cloxacillin, OFX: Ofloxacin, CIP: Ciprofloxacin.

Table 5: Biofilm formation capability of *Klebsiella* spp. Isolated from Snail on Aluminum and Plastic surfaces

Benin			Sapele		
Isolates	Aluminum (OD)	Plastic (OD)	Isolates	Aluminum (OD)	Plastic (OD)
KSB1	1.147(S)	3.412(S)	KSS1	0.615(S)	3.419(S)
KSB2	0.849(S)	1.161(S)	KSS2	0.629(S)	3.446(S)
KSB3	0.715(S)	3.450(S)	KSS3	0.849(S)	2.161(S)
KSB4	1.517(S)	3.419(S)	KSS4	0.621(S)	3.492(S)
KSB5	0.667(S)	1.662(S)	KSS5	1.517(S)	3.462(S)
KSB6	0.695(S)	3.168(S)	KSS6	0.846(S)	2.882(S)
KSB7	1.443(S)	2.916(S)	KSS7	1.458(S)	3.156(S)
KSB8	0.756(S)	3.428(S)	KSS8	0.646(S)	3.415(S)
KSB9	0.615(S)	3.414(S)	KSS9	0.757(S)	2.944(S)
Nil	Nil	Nil	KSS10	1.296(S)	3.352(S)
Mean OD	0.934(S)	2.892(S)	Mean OD	0.923(S)	3.173(S)

Key: KSB = *Klebsiella* sp. Isolate from Snail Benin; KSS = *Klebsiella* sp. Isolate from Snail Sapele; OD = Optical Density

Biofilm classification

S: Strong: >0.308; **M:** Moderate: 0.154-0.308; **W:** Weak: 0.077-0.154; **N:** Non Adherent: <0.077

Table 5: Biofilm formation capability of *Klebsiella* spp. Isolated from Edible worm on Aluminum and plastic surfaces

Benin			Sapele		
Isolates	Aluminum (OD)	Plastic (OD)	Isolates	Aluminum (OD)	Plastic (OD)
KEB1	0.629 (S)	3.446(S)	KES1	0.812(S)	1.237(S)
KEB2	0.041(N)	1.250(S)	KES2	0.152(W)	1.215(S)
KEB3	0.859(S)	1.261(S)	KES3	0.630(S)	3.491(S)
KEB4	0.148(M)	3.386(S)	KES4	1.524(S)	3.385(S)
KEB5	0.662(S)	3.412(S)	KES5	0.111(W)	1.359(S)
KEB6	0.078(W)	1.314(S)	KES6	0.066(N)	2.142(S)
KEB7	0.798(S)	2.236(S)	KES7	0.488(S)	2.514(S)
KEB8	0.846(S)	2.496(S)	KES8	0.875(S)	3.474(S)
KEB9	0.855(S)	3.361(S)	KES9	1.126(S)	2.991(S)
KEB10	0.088(W)	2.098(S)	KES10	0.634(S)	3.283(S)
Mean OD	0.500(S)	2.426(S)	Mean OD	0.642 (S)	2.509(S)

Key: KEB = *Klebsiella* sp. Isolate from Edible worm Benin; KES = *Klebsiella* sp. Isolate from Edible worm Sapele; OD = Optical Density

Biofilm classification

S: Strong: >0.308; **M:** Moderate: 0.154-0.308; **W:** Weak: 0.077-0.154; **N:** Non Adherent: <0.077

DISCUSSION

The genus *Klebsiella* is an opportunistic microorganism that has been extensively studied in clinical and environmental settings, where they have been variously reported to be responsible for clinical conditions such as bacteremia, pneumonia and urinary tract infections (Karlowsky *et al.*, 2015; Hartantyo *et al.*, 2020). Some species are recognized as an important multidrug-resistant (MDR) pathogen affecting humans and are a major source for hospital infections associated with high morbidity and mortality due to limited treatment options (Navon-Venezia *et al.*, 2017). With the increasing observation that *Klebsiella* species are emerging as important food borne infectious agent worldwide, this investigation was initiated to add to the body of knowledge on the presence of the organism in some food sources in Nigeria, especially ready to eat foods which are eaten direct without further processing. The result of the study shows that *Klebsiella* spp. was present in over 95% of the two food types (edible worm had 100% while snail had 95%). The high prevalent rates of *Klebsiella* spp. in this study should be of concern to health authorities especially for the fact that snail and edible worm are ready to eat food materials consumed directly without further processing and the fact too that a large number of persons buy and consume these foods because of its nutritional benefits (Fasoranti, 1998; Onyeike *et al.*, 2005). It is suggestive to note that this high prevalent rate could be attributed to cross contamination due to the method of sales of these food products after processing with heat and some spices. It was observed that they were hawked and sold in the open along the major highways without proper packaging except being wrapped with thin cellophane materials.

The problem of drug resistance among food borne pathogens has become a very serious cause for concern among microbiologists and health officials as the phenomenon is increasingly making treatments of infectious diseases with popular and regular antimicrobials no longer effective. *Klebsiella* spp. have been variously found especially in clinical samples to exhibit not only drug resistance but high propensity to develop multidrug resistance to popular antibiotics (Navon-Venezia *et al.*, 2017). The antibacterial resistance pattern in this study shows that the *Klebsiella* isolates were resistant to some commonly used antibiotics (table 4). Interestingly it was observed that the isolates

had very high resistance (over 90%) to some popular antibiotics such as ampicillin, cefuroxime, amoxicillin and doxycycline and at the same time were also completely susceptible (100%) to drugs such as gentamycin, ofloxacin and ciprofloxacin. This display of multidrug resistance among isolates from these food materials are quite worrisome given the fact that the food materials are harvested from natural wide sources making contact with antibiotic use in rearing or cultivating them almost impossible. The observed multidrug resistance could however be traced to stress adaptation capabilities of the isolates as observed by Capozzi *et al.* (2009) who opined that stress conditions such as cold, heat and acid stresses and freeze injuries among others may trigger several mechanisms in bacterial cells which may include stress adaptation, cellular repair and even enhanced virulence. In spite of the multidrug resistant nature of the isolates however it's a thing of joy to note that they were not resistant to some of the fluoroquinolones (Ofloxacin and Ciprofloxacin) which are antibiotics of choice when some others fail in treating enteric infections arising from organisms such as *Klebsiella* spp.

Biofilms are microbial communities attached to surfaces and most often are embedded in an extracellular polymeric substance which provides for the protection, stability and nutrients of the various bacterial species indwelling (Wilson *et al.*, 2018). Because of the significant role that biofilms play in the clinical, industrial and natural settings, the interest in studying them has increased drastically and today many infections are known to be biofilm associated (Basak *et al.*, 2013). Biofilm producing capability of *Klebsiella* spp. studied in this investigation, shows that over 90% of the isolates were strong biofilm producers. A similar report by Nirwati *et al.*, 2019, stated that 148 (85.63%) of 167 isolates in their study were biofilm producers. Hassan *et al.* (2011) similarly reported that over 64.7% of the *Klebsiella* isolates were identified as high or moderate biofilm producers. In another study, Seifi *et al.* (2016) reported that 93.6% of *K. pneumoniae* isolated in their study were biofilm producers and only 6.4% were not biofilm producers. An interesting result from the study was the observation that all the isolates were stronger biofilm producers on Plastic surfaces than the aluminum surfaces (tables 4 and 5). This capacity of microorganisms to form biofilm at varying degree at different surfaces could be traced to some factors which include but not limited to the

physicochemical characteristic of *Klebsiella* spp., physical interaction between the constituents, the type of surface where the biofilm attaches, temperature and pH as observed by Nirwati *et al.* (2019). In this study plastic materials show more affinity for biofilm formation than aluminum surfaces. Kaczorek *et al.* (2008) suggested in their study that hydrophobic materials are observed to be surfaces that provide greater bacterial adherence than hydrophilic materials. Surfaces such as aluminum are hydrophobic in nature as such are likely to result in less capacity for microorganisms to produce biofilms on them than plastic surfaces which are hydrophilic in nature, a phenomenon that was observed in this study.

Conclusively, it is noteworthy to state that the presence of such an emerging foodborne pathogen with such a high prevalence rate in ready to eat edible worm and snail which are eaten directly without further processing is significant and presents a potential health challenge to the populace. More so the isolates were not only highly resistant to some popularly used antibiotics, but were also strong producers of biofilm, a combination that makes treatment of infection difficult to achieve. It is therefore recommended that good manufacturing practice and appropriate packaging be done in the production and sale of such ready to eat food products. Also education of the public on the danger of indiscriminate purchase and consumption of such food materials hawked on the street and highway is highly advocated as it has now been established that eating such foods can result in being infected with pathogens such as *Klebsiella* spp. and other food borne infectious agents.

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